

ANCIENT EGYPTIAN GARDEN-PARK ART

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Abstract. *This article describes the history of the ancient Egyptian garden parks, their origin, and the composition of the Egyptian gardens. Such general concepts as the ancient Egyptian garden, an organic combination of religious, utilitarian and aesthetic functions are highlighted. The ancient Egyptians created an advanced irrigation system, built canals that supplied water to fields, and hydraulic structures that protected cities and settlements from floods during river floods. Magnificent palaces, majestic and durable temple complexes, pyramids, partially preserved to the present day, were built from valuable building materials - granite, limestone, sandstone, etc., which Ancient Egypt is rich in. Architectural monuments of the Ancient Kingdom (ABB.28-23 centuries BC) pyramids of the pharaohs and tombs of the nobility, temples with columns in the form of lotus, palm, papyrus (pyramids of Giza: Cheops, Chephren and Mycerinus. The Middle Kingdom (ABB.21-18vv) stone tombs decorated with paintings on traditional themes. The shapes of temples with two rows of columns and a high middle part. The New Kingdom (XVI-XI centuries BC) – temples consisted of a sanctuary, a closed hall with columns and a closed courtyard surrounded by a blank wall. Gardens were very common in Egypt. The houses of the nobility were always surrounded by gardens, which varied in location and wealth depending on the condition of the owner. Especially large and rich gardens belonged to the kings. Temples of the gods are usually surrounded by luxurious gardens, and funds for their creation often came from kings. For example, the Harris papyrus says that Ramses III ordered large and luxurious gardens to be laid out for the temples of the gods of Heliopolis. "For your temple, vol... I have built large gardens planted with grapes and cabbage soup... I have created alleys of olive trees in your city. I have provided these seedlings to gardeners and many technicians who will make the purest Egyptian oil needed to light the lamps in your luxurious temple. I gave you pistachio groves and ponds covered with lotuses, sitnikas, herbs and flowers from different countries — Tetmer, An-Haut — fragrant and pleasant to look at your magnificent face. Currently, interest in Garden and Park art is growing rapidly, which, along with new research in the field of Garden and park art, forces us to also assimilate the legacy of the past in order to be able to extract from this heritage everything that is valuable to us. The history of parks and parks of different eras and peoples is covered in the literature 1) not in the same detail. There is the most detailed information about parks and parks of the XVI—XVIII centuries. In this article, we will give a description of ancient Egyptian and Assyro-Babylonian gardens and parks based on the study of some literary and artistic monuments of Egypt and Assyria-Babylon.*

Keywords:

Ancient Egypt, Gardens, Nile Valley, hanging garden, Assyria, temples, Pleasure Gardens, temples, compositional features, pyramids.

Introduction

Ancient Egypt was established as an independent state in the 4th millennium BC. The development of the state is closely linked to the Nile Valley, which carries its waters from south to north into the Mediterranean Sea. The valley was naturally dominated by tamarixes and palm trees, and the Nile by reeds, papyri, and lotuses. Hot and arid climate, hot winds, almost no

precipitation, excluded the presence of tree-shrub plants in some important areas. The ancient Egyptians created a developed irrigation system, canals supplying water to the fields, and hydrotechnical devices that protect cities and settlements from flooding during river floods. Of the valuable building materials rich in Ancient Egypt - granite, limestone, sandstone and others, magnificent palaces, durable temple complexes and pyramids were built, which partially survive to this day.

Ancient Egypt is characterized by huge monumental structures that glorify Pharaohs. The most ancient monuments are located in the delta of the Nile Valley, which is due to the fact that the beginning of Egyptian civilization was located in this very place. In Egypt, building materials used clay-covered reeds, Nile Valley clay bricks, and straw, while monumental structures used stone. Artistic forms and pictorial motifs were taken from nature by the Egyptians: the sun, Lotus, papyrus, Palm, Lions had a mainly religious purpose. Monuments of the architecture of the ancient kingdom (3rd century BC).28th-23rd centuries) pharaonic pyramids and Noble tombs, Lotus-shaped, palm-shaped, papyrus-shaped pillared temples (Giza Pyramids: Cheops, Hephren and Mikerin. The middle kingdom (avv.21 18vv) rock tombs decorated with paintings on traditional themes. Forms of chapels with two rows of columns and a high middle part. New Kingdom (16th-11th centuries BC) – temples consisted of a sanctuary, a hall with an enclosed column, and an enclosed courtyard surrounded by an empty wall.

Analysis of thematic literature (Literature review).

On this topic, K.D Rahimov, A.S Uraiov, textbook “design of objects of Landscape Architect”. Tashkent; "Psalm-standard", 2015. - 224 b. Avtor: starshiy prepodavatel café " Das " Dobronravova E.A. Uchebnoe posobie. Chast 1. (STR. 114., TASI 2009). Rakhimov, K.D. Educational guide” modern directions of Garden-park design " / K.Rakhimov. Tashkent: "celebrity-press", 2017. Rakhimov K.D., Uralov A.S. Design of objects of Landscape Architecture. - T., 2015. S.S.Ojegov, A.S.Uralov, K.J.Rakhimov. Landscape architecture and design.. Samarkand, 2003. the study was carried out by Lar adaboyots and research.

Analysis and Results (Results and discussion).

At this time, the gardens are regular: it is usually a walled Square area, trees are planted along its perimeter, in the central part there is a vineyard; there are also rectangular pools for storing fish and waterfowl.

The ancient Egyptian Garden was characterized by an organic combination of religious, utilitarian and aesthetic functions.

In general, garden art was formed in Ancient Egypt with clear compositional and planning laws:

- regular plan, which involves the construction of the composition axial and the use of symmetry;
- formation of closed compositions;
- the presence of water bodies as an integral and often basic part of the garden;
- use of rhythm as a compositional tool;
- use of alleys and ordinary seedlings;
- the use of exotics in the assortment of woody plants.

Assyrian and Babylonian States (Mesopotamia) (8th-7th centuries BC). The main material for construction is fragile raw brick. The cities were created in a round, and later rectangular shape, surrounded by two-or three-ring fortress walls. Based on the location of Babylon, there are 8 wide streets leading to the city gates. From them, a wide street leads to a certain temple .

Figure 1. Ancient Egyptian Gardens

Temples are secondary elements of the composition. On the terraces, the construction was used for ziggurat temples in the form of towers with stairs. On their lower platforms, plants are planted in pits with plant soils along the perimeter.

In Ancient Egypt, the first "Pleasure Gardens" appeared in rich priests. Resting in the shade of trees and enjoying the taste of fruits, their images can be seen in ancient Egyptian frescoes.

A variety of fragrant flowers were grown in the priestly Gardens, the surface of the ponds covered with lotuses and nymphs. And in the era of Cleopatra, garden roses were often grown.

Everyone knows the Hanging Gardens of Babylon in Babylon. The structure consisted of 4 terraces raised one above the other. Trees were planted on the bottom two terraces, and shrubs and flowers at the top.

The "Hanging Gardens" of Semiramis were located in the courtyard of the palace of King Nebuchadnezzar and consisted of a series of high terraces: trees at the bottom, shrubs and flowers at the top. There were also extensive parks for hunting and horseback riding. (prototype of modern forest parks).

E. BC. Near the city of Hirsabad, trees brought from other countries grew in it: cypress, cedar, maple, Willow, Poplar, Laurel, boxwood, fruit trees. There are also records of extensive parks or forests, mainly for hunting and horseback riding. These massifs are prototypes of modern forest parks.

Figure 3. A bouncy garden look that originated in Ancient Egypt.

The Hanging Gardens of Semiramis are one of the Seven Wonders of the world. A more correct name for this structure is hanging gardens (amitis Springs — Semiramis; according to the third sources — Amanis): this is how the wife of the Babylonian king Nebuchadnezzar p was named, for which Gardens were created. It is assumed that they were located in the ancient State of Babylon, near the modern city of Hill, Iraq. According to an alternative version based on the reopening of cuneiform inscriptions, they may have been located in Nineveh, the capital of the Assyrian Kingdom, and were built in the early 7th century BC. They are the wonder of the world that existed for the shortest time. The forces of King Nebuchadnezzar P of Babylon (605-562 BC) formed a military alliance with King Kiahar of the Medes to fight the main enemy of Assyria, who had twice destroyed the capital of the Babylonian state.

After their defeat, they divided Assyrian territory between themselves. Their military alliance was confirmed by the marriage of Nebuchadnezzar to the daughter of Amitis, King of the Medes. The dusty and noisy Babylon, located on a bare sandy plain, did not please the queen, who grew up in the mountainous and green mussels. To comfort him, Nebuchadnezzar P ordered the construction of Hanging Gardens. However, in historical science, the name of the gardens is incorrectly given to the Assyrian Queen Semiramis, who lived two centuries ago.

Figure 4. Semiramis Gardens

Gardens in ancient Egypt are common. Perhaps due to the vegetable gardens irrigated by the Nile River, as the prosperity of Egypt increased, they became luxurious complexes with ponds, flowers, statues, shady alleys of fruit trees. The gardens were built around the temples, palaces and castles of wealthy Egyptians. In addition, the tombs were known as Tomb gardens around them.

The history and development of ancient Egyptian gardens, like other aspects of ancient Egyptian life, was associated with the Nile River and the network of canals that fed it. The oldest Gardens in Egypt were flower beds and vegetable gardens, which belonged to temples that cultivated vegetables for certain rituals. During the Middle Kingdom, large garden complexes and pleasure gardens around the estates of wealthy Egyptians appear around the palace Tsartfarons.

The layout of the Egyptian Garden. Images of Egyptian gardens are found on tomb walls, some papyri, and sarcophagi. The composition of Egyptian Gardens was based mainly on the principle of geometric structures. Gardens were often laid out on level ground and rarely on terraces.

The gardens were rectangular and symmetrically planned. A distinctive feature of Egyptian Gardens is the pond, which is often located in the middle. The Pharaohs ' Palace Gardens may have many pools, including wide enough to row. The ponds were Artificial with banks covered with stone slabs. The pond was overgrown with aquatic plants, and fish and waterfowl were grown. Pavilions, gazebos and churches for domestic deities were built near the ponds.

Extensive gardens were built around the temples. There were twenty-six vegetable gardens, as well as an ancient Botanical Garden, which contained the inscriptions “beautiful flowers and strange plants of all kinds found in the blessed land conquered by His Majesty”.

Temple gardens often had alleys of fig palms and plantains (dedicated to the Temple Of Love Hathor). Sometimes rows of trees stretched for several kilometers, connecting the various temples. For trees planted away from the river, it was necessary to dig wells up to ten meters deep. Flowers for religious ceremonies were grown in the gardens, as well as medicinal plants and spices such as cumin, licorice and coriander.

The palace gardens were very large, with many ponds and shady alleys for the rest of the Pharaohs. The rulers of Ancient Egypt were brought from other countries, planting unknown plants in Egypt in gardens. For example, Queen Hatshepsut sent an expedition to the Land of Punt, which, along with Ivory, myrtle and incense, brought myrtle trees dug with roots from the ground.

From the time of the New Kingdom, Pleasure Gardens were a common feature of the lavish estates of wealthy Egyptians. In the center was a rectangular pond, surrounded by a row of trees in succession. The edges of the ponds are inclined to stairs, allowing gardeners to collect water for irrigation. The pond is often surrounded by vineyards and is surrounded by walls or columns decorated with colorful paintings of people, animals and plants.

Figure 4. A bouncy garden look that originated in Ancient Egypt.

Conclusions and suggestions (Conclusion).

In conclusion, Ancient Egypt amazes, Awakens imagination, inspires. Gone are the days when knowledge of Ancient Egypt was preserved for a small group of insiders. Now every amateur enthusiast can get acquainted with the secrets of hieroglyphs, the history of a fascinating civilization, admire the magnificent buildings, mausoleums of the country on the Nile River.

In the Nile River valleys, spruce, fir, dates, figs, tamarix, Poplar, tar were grown. But this was not enough for complete comfort. It was necessary to create gardens that bring coolness and shade. "He is poor, he has no shadow" - this is what ancient texts say. The absence of shadow is one of the most severe plagues of the poor in this country. In hot climates, the organization of gardens required artificial irrigation. Figs, mulberries, almonds, dates, grapes

were grown in a simple, rectangular network of canals that required the creation of rectangular, symmetrically laid Gardens.

A distinctive feature of Egyptian Gardens was the fact that vegetables and flowers occupy almost all the space between the trees. Egyptian gardeners were engaged not only in cultivation, but also in forcing lilies, gillyflowers and roses of the Valley. Minyonet, poppy, cornflower, chamomile, lilies, chrysanthemums have grown in Egyptian Gardens. The lily flower was a symbol of hope and the brevity of life, from which fragrant oil was obtained. Flowers were widely used for artistic decoration of holidays, from which wreaths and garlands were woven. During the reign of Queen Cleopatra (69-30 BC), special attention was paid to the cultivation of various roses.

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